

Bromination of Substances Containing two Aromatic Nuclei. Part I. Bromination of Cresyl and Nitrophenyl Benzoates.

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The object of the present work is to investigate the positions taken up by bromine on entering a molecule containing two aromatic nuclei. Kauschke (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1895, ii, 51, 210) found that phenyl and cresyl benzoates are readily brominated but he did not establish the constitution of the products. In this work the cresyl esters are brominated according to the method of Kauschke (*loc. cit.*) and it is found that the use of fuming nitric acid (*d* 1.45) as a carrier, according to Varma and Pannicker (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 500) is advantageous.

The constitution of the products has been established by hydrolysis and synthesis from the respective acid chloride and cresols. *o*-, *m*-, *p*-Cresyl benzoates yield respectively 4-bromo-2-methyl, 4-bromo-3-methyl- and 2-bromo-4-methylphenyl benzoates.

With nitrophenyl benzoates, the nitro group so deactivates its nucleus that bromine enters the acidic rings. Resistance to bromination is marked, so that the usual carriers are found ineffective, and reaction could be brought about only in presence of fuming nitric acid (*d* 1.45). *o*-, *m*-, *p*-Nitrophenyl benzoates yield the corresponding nitrophenyl *m*-bromobenzoate, when the reacting substances are in molecular proportion (1:1).

If the ester and bromine are used in molecular proportion of 1:2, *o*- and *m*-nitrophenyl benzoates yield the respective nitrophenyl 2:5-dibromobenzoates; while the *para* isomer under these conditions yields only monobromo derivative. *p*-Nitrophenyl 2:5-dibromobenzoate can, however, be obtained by brominating *p*-nitrophenyl *m*-bromo benzoate.

The constitution of these esters has been established by hydrolysis.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Bromo-2-methylphenyl benzoate.—To a mixture of *o*-cresyl benzoate (8 g.) and bromine (6 g.), fuming nitric acid (*d* 1.45, 10 c.c.) was gradually added and the whole heated on a water-bath with a reflux condenser for about 4 hours. The mixture was diluted with water and neutralised with sodium carbonate when a solid separated. It crystallised from alcohol in cream coloured needles, *m. p.* 65°, yield 55%. It is soluble in common organic solvents. Kauschke (*loc. cit.*) gives *m. p.* 59°. (Found: Br, 27.4. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2Br$ requires Br, 27.5 per cent).

The mixed melting point of the ester with synthetic 4-bromo-2-methylphenyl benzoate (Jadhav and Rangwala, *Bombay Univ. J.*, 1934, 3, 161), showed no lowering.

Hydrolysis.—The bromo ester (4 g.) was boiled with alcoholic caustic potash solution (6 g. in 50 c. c.) for 10 hours. The solution was acidified and alcohol removed. The solid obtained was treated with sodium carbonate solution, the aqueous layer separated from the oil and acidified, when a solid separated. It was crystallised from hot water and identified as benzoic acid. The oil must, therefore, be 4-bromo-*o*-cresol.

4-Bromo-3-methylphenyl benzoate was prepared in the same way as the *o*-cresyl isomer, the mixture being heated for 8 hours. The paste obtained after dilution and neutralisation solidified on keeping in the refrigerator. It crystallises from alcohol in needles, *m. p.* 82-3°, yield 70%. (Found: Br, 27.3. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2Br$ requires Br, 27.5 per cent).

The mixed melting point of the bromo ester with authentic 4-bromo-2-methylphenyl benzoate (Walter and Zipper, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1915, 91, ii, 377) showed no lowering. Benzoic acid was obtained by the hydrolysis of the ester.

2-Bromo-4-methylphenylbenzoate.—Bromination was effected by heating the ester with bromine for 10 hours without fuming nitric acid, which did not improve the yield. The product is a thick oil which is difficult to distil. It solidifies below 0°, yield 60%. (Found: Br, 27.5. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2Br$ requires Br, 27.5 per cent).

The substance gave benzoic acid on hydrolysis and the cryslic portion had *b. p.* 219-21°. (Found: Br, 42.5. C_7H_7O Br requires Br, 42.8 per cent).

The boiling points for 2-bromo-*p*-cresol given in the literature are 218-20° (Henninger, *Ber.*, 1882, 16, 1081); 218-14° (Schall and Dralle, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 2530; Stormer and Gohl, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 2875); 218-19° (Zincke and Wiederhold, *Annalen*, 1902, 320, 203).

o-Nitrophenyl *m*-bromobenzoate.—To a mixture of *o*-nitrophenylbenzoate (12 g.) and bromine (8 g.), fuming nitric acid (*d* 1.45, 20 c.c.) was gradually added and the whole was refluxed for about 5 hours on a water-bath. The reaction product was poured into water and neutralised with sodium carbonate. The solid obtained crystallises from alcohol in cream coloured plates, m. p. 105°, yield 45 %. It is soluble in acetone, chloroform and benzene, sparingly so in carbon tetrachloride, alcohol and acetic acid. (Found: Br, 24.6. $C_{13}H_8O_4$ NBr requires Br, 24.8 per cent).

The ester was hydrolysed by boiling with aqueous caustic potash solution (about 20%) for 2 hours. The solution was acidified and *o*-nitrophenol was removed by steam distillation, and the acid, crystallised from the hot solution on cooling, melted at 155-156°. It was identified as *m*-bromobenzoic acid by mixed melting point with an authentic sample.

m-Nitrophenyl *m*-bromo-benzoate was prepared in the same way as the *o*-isomer. The solid obtained crystallises from acetic acid in white needles, m. p. 132°, yield 50 %. Its solubility resembles that of the *ortho* isomer. (Found: Br, 24.6. $C_{13}H_8O_4$ NBr requires Br, 24.8 per cent).

The acid obtained by hydrolysis was identified as *m*-bromobenzoic acid (mixed m. p.). The nitrophenol being soluble in water, the solution was evaporated to dryness and the residue extracted with ether. It was found to be *m*-nitrophenol (mixed m. p.).

p-Nitrophenyl *m*-bromobenzoate was prepared in the same way as above. The solid obtained crystallises from acetic acid in white needles, m. p. 122°, yield 50 %. Its solubility resembles that of its other isomers. (Found: Br, 24.7. $C_{13}H_8O_4$ NBr requires Br, 24.8 per cent). The products of hydrolysis were identified as *m*-bromobenzoic and *p*-nitrophenol (mixed m. p.).

o-Nitrophenyl 2:5-dibromobenzoate.—To a mixture of *o*-nitrophenyl benzoate (12 g.) and bromine (16 g.) fuming nitric acid (*d* 1.45, 20 c. c.) was gradually added and the mixture was heated with a reflux condenser for about 12 hours. After dilution and neutralisation with sodium carbonate, a pasty mass was obtained which solidified in the refrigerator. It crystallises from acetic acid in white

needles, m. p. 182°, yield 40 %. It resembles the monobromo derivative in solubility. (Found : Br, 39.6. $C_{13}H_7O_4NBr_2$ requires Br, 39.9 per cent).

The products of hydrolysis were identified as 2:5 dibromobenzoic acid (Claus and Reh, *Annalen*, 1891, 266, 207) and *o*-nitrophenol (mixed m. p.).

m-Nitrophenyl 2:5-dibromobenzoate was prepared in the same way as the *ortho* isomer by heating the mixture for 8 hours, yield 60%. It crystallises from glacial acetic acid in white needles, m. p. 165°. It resembles the *ortho* isomer in solubility. (Found : Br, 39.8. $C_{13}H_7O_4NBr_2$ requires Br, 39.9 per cent)

This compound can also be prepared by brominating *m*-nitrophenyl *m*-bromobenzoate in presence of fuming nitric acid, but the yield is poor.

The products of hydrolysis were identified as 2:5-dibromobenzoic acid and *m*-nitrophenol (mixed m. p.).

p-Nitrophenyl 2:5-dibromobenzoate.—To a mixture of *p*-nitrophenyl *m*-bromobenzoate (8 g.) and bromine (4.5 g.), fuming nitric acid (*d* 1.45, 12 c. c.) was gradually added, and the mixture heated with a reflux condenser on a water bath for 7 hours. The solid, obtained by treating the reaction mixture in the usual way, crystallises from acetone in bright needles, m. p. 183-84°, yield 35 per cent. It is sparingly soluble in acetone, chloroform and in alcohol, benzene and acetic acid. (Found : Br, 39.6. $C_{13}H_7O_4NBr_2$ requires Br, 39.9 per cent). This substance cannot be obtained directly from the original ester.

The products of hydrolysis were identified as 2:5-dibromo-benzoic acid and *p*-nitrophenol (mixed m. p.).

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